

INVESTIGATION OF THE PROCESS AND MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF POLYETHERSULFONE/CARBON FIBER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper describes polyethersulfone (PES)/carbon fiber composites. PES resin was dissolved in a mixed solvent to get solution of PES resin. Prepreg was produced in a winding machine. After drying of PES/carbon prepreg, we molded the stack of prepreg to make composite laminates. The results of investigation showed that PES/carbon composites possessed an excellent bonding of fiber to the resin and high shear and flexural properties.

INTRODUCTION

Advanced thermoplastic composites were new composites which emerged in the early 70s. Advanced thermoplastic composites are continuous long fiber or fabric reinforced high performance thermoplastics (such as polyethersulfone, polyetherether-ketone etc.). The success of such composites fills the gap between short fiber reinforced plastics and thermoset composites. They not only possess the toughness and processability of short fiber reinforced plastics but also the high strength and stiffness of thermoset composites.

Home-made PES plastic products have been put into use for several years. But as a matrix of composite it is still under research. First there are a great deal of difficulties in making PES/CF prepreg. Consolidation conditions used in fabricating thermoplastic composites are much different from those in fabricating thermoset matrix composites. In particular their molding temperature must be high and they need special cooling equipment to guarantee the quality of laminates.

In this paper a wet-method is used to fabricate PES/CF prepreg and then layer it in laminate structure. The stack is pressed. Mechanical properties are tested in accordance with GB*. The bonding of fiber to the resin is analysed through SEM photographs of fracture surface. Results indicate that it is practicable to use a wet-method to produce prepreg of PES/CF and press them into laminates.

1. EXPERIMENTS

Materials

1.1. Carbon fiber

a. T-300 made in Japan, tensile strength 2892 MPa, tensile modulus 1.89×10^5 MPa, specific weight 1.74 kg/cm^2 .

b. Carbon fiber made in Liaoyuan, tensile strength 2794 MPa, specific weight 1.78 kg/cm^2 , carbon content 93%.

*GB is the National Standard of China.

1.2. Polyethersulfone

- a. Produced by Chemistry Department of Jilin University.
- b. Produced by Chemical Raw Material Company of Wuhan.

1.3. Solvent

- a. N,N-dimethylacetamide, reagent grade, produced by Beijing Chemical Company.
- b. Acetone, industry grade.

Preparation of Specimen

PES resin is dissolved in a mixed solvent. Prepreg (unidirectional cloth) is produced with a winding machine and dried in a baking oven.

Prepreg plies are stacked according to designed laminate structure in a preheated mold. Then the stack is molded on a press to get composite laminates. Pressing parameters are: temperature 320°C, pressure 6 MPa, time 25 min, demold below 150°C.

2. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

2.1. The tensile performance of PES/CF composite

0° tensile specimens are shattered to many fabric straps. This indicates that the interface of PES/CF composites is damaged by shear stress. Experimental results also indicate that the fracture of different laminate structure specimens belongs to ductile rupture. Table 1 lists the data of the tensile strength and modulus of PES/CF composites.

Table 1 Tensile properties of PES (Wuhan)/T-300 Composites.

Laminate structure	0°	90°	(0°/90°)	[(+45°/-45°)/+45°] _{4s}
Tensile strength MPa	1048.60	35.83	456.38	
Tensile modulus MPa	110936	67620	59584	
Passion ratio				0.322
Short beam shear strength				61.48
Short beam shear modulus				5096

2.2. Interlaminar shear performance of PES/CF composites

The most common fracture forms of PES/CF composites in shear tests are flexural rupture rather than delamination. After loaded specimens bring about cracks or local plastic deformation. Because the bonding of carbon fiber to PES is very good, cracks can not easily propagate in the interlaminar direction, (do not result in delamination) cracks can only propagate along the transverse direction of specimens. Cracks run into fibers and break them. This gives rise to a flexural rupture mode. If local plastic deformation rather than cracks appear after loaded the resulted fracture would be arc-fracture. Why do these two shear results take place? On one hand, it is because the adhesion between fiber and the resin is good, interface strength is high and it does not delaminate. On the other hand we consider that there may be some problems in applying thermoset composite test standards to thermoplastic composites. Of course up to now no test standards for thermoplastic composites has been established. Further research is still required.

Table 2 shows the influence of temperature on shear performance of PES/CF composites. We can see that shear strength decreases a lot as temperature is increased. It might be that PES resin brings about deformation which gives rise to debonding of fiber to PES resin.

2.3. Flexural properties of PES/CF composites

The flexural strength and modulus of PES/CF composites are high despite the great deflection (7-8mm). Table 3 lists the flexural data. Figure 1 shows the curve between local loading and deflection. We can see that the curve is smooth in the position of P=Pmax. This indicates PES/CF composites have ductile rupture.

Table 2. Effect of temperature on the shear strength of PES/CF composites

No.	Shear strength (MPa)			
	23°C	80°C	120°C	160°C
1	84.51	51.25	39.21	36.44
2	54.56	44.71	34.07	30.05
3	77.45	57.25	48.90	45.18
4	76.23	62.65	48.81	40.92
5	66.22	51.24	37.98	25.21
6	66.24	54.04	38.14	35.70
7	65.34	45.15	42.34	36.27
8	76.23	55.64	48.86	46.21
9	70.35	51.76	47.46	40.00

Figure 1. Flexural load-deflection curve of PES/CF composite

Table 3. Flexural properties of PES/CF composites

Flexural strength MPa	2283.75	2330.90	1485.58	1497.37	1938.25	1226.00
Discrete ratio %	11.02	8.37	5.83	2.90	3.32	2.78
Flexural modulus GPa	127.40	192.03	134.26	109.76	120.54	81.34
Discrete ratio %	6.92	5.25	8.85	3.30	1.2	7.33

2.4. Dynamic mechanical characterization of PES/CF composites

Figure 2 is a dynamic mechanical spectrum of PES (Jilin)/T-300 composites. Figure 3 is a dynamic mechanical spectrum of PES (Jilin)/CF (Liaoyuan) composites.

The tensile storage modulus of PES (Jilin)/T-300 composites is 0.20×10^5 MPa higher than PES (Jilin)/CF (Liaoyuan) composites. We also find out that annealing can enhance their modulus. Figure 4 shows the influence of annealing on dynamic mechanical performance of PES/CF composites.

2.5. Analysis of fracture surface of PES/CF composites.

Producing prepreg is a difficult step in the forming of thermoplastic composites.⁴ The concentration of PES resin in the solution is the key. On the base of certain concentration of PES resin, we choose proper molding conditions to mold composite laminates. We reach the following conclusion through analysis of SEM photographs of fracture surface of

Fig. 2. DMA spectrum of PES/T-300 composites.

Fig.3. DMA spectrum of PES/CF (Liaoyuan) composites.

laminates. Figure 5 shows when PES/T-300 fractures there is no delamination between fiber and the resin, indicating that shear strength of PES is higher than its tensile strength. So there is resin on the fracture surface, and no debonding exists. Figure 6 shows the damage of interface of homemade carbon fiber composites. No delamination is found. Figure 7 shows the good adhesion between fiber and PES resin of the same laminate. Figure 8 shows the case that fiber slips from PES resin and at the same time fiber surface peeled, resulting a rough fiber surface. This point is different from the result obtained by Yuchai Ke etc.⁵

3. CONCLUSIONS

A. It is practicable using a mixed solvent of N,N-dimethylacetamide and acetone to dissolve PES resin and producing PES/CF prepreg with a wet-method.

B. The optimum processing parameters of PES/CF composites are as following:

For PES/T-300 composites: Temperature 320°C, Pressure 6 MPa, Time 25 minutes.

For PES/CF (homemade) composites: Temperature 300°C, Pressure 6 MPa, Time 25 minutes.

PES/CF composites show high shear and flexural strength and high flexural modulus.

C. Analysis of composites fracture surface proved that drying before molding and choosing proper processing parameters can result in good bond-

- Curve 1. PES/T-300 composite controled.
- Curve 2. PES/T-300 composite annealed for two hours at 180°C.
- Curve 3. PES/T-300 composite annealed for two hours at 200°C.

Fig. 4. DMA spectrum of PES/T-300 after annealed

Fig. 5. SEM photograph of the fracture surface of PES/T-300 composite

Fig.6. SEM photograph of the fracture surface of PES/CF (Liaoyuan) composite

Fig.7. SEM photograph of the fracture surface of PES/CF (Liaoyuan) composite

Fig.8. SEM photograph of the fracture surface of PES/CF (Liaoyuan) composite

ing of fiber to PES resin.

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